

A Study on Area, Production and Marketing of Apples in Kashmir

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ABSTRACT

Horticulture is the science and art of growing plants, vegetables, fruits, flowers and any other cultivar. Kashmir which is known as paradise on earth is locally famous for its horticulture production. Kashmiri horticulture has grown by leaps and bounds in the past few years. Apple cultivation is a main crop of Kashmiri horticulture. Apple cultivation is considered as a highly profitable and attractive economic activity in Kashmir. Apple industry plays an important role in the employment generation in the region as it provides employment to nearly 30 lakh people either directly or indirectly which suggests that nearly half of the population of a region is engaged in the apple cultivation either directly or indirectly. The aim of a present paper is to analyze the district wise apple production in Kashmir, the total area under the apple cultivation, and the dispatch of apple fruit to different markets of the country as well as abroad from the fruit mandi sopore(largest fruit mandi in Kashmir).

Keywords: *Apple, Area, Production, Marketing*

Introduction

Apple is considered as a king of all fruits as it has been associated with the Biblical story of *Adam & Eve* between the Caspian and the Black sea, the Middle East just about 4000 yrs ago. It is one of the oldest varieties in existence; a research study states that humans have enjoyed apples ever since at least 6500(BC). There are more than 7500 known cultivars of apples. China is the largest apple producing country in the World, contributes over 50% of total production of the World while, India is ranked as the 6th largest apple producing country in the World & 2nd in Asia.

Introduction of apple industry in India

Apple was introduced in India by the British in KULLU valley of the Himalayan state of Himachal Pradesh as far back as 1865, while the colored “Delicious” cultivar of Apple was introduced to SHIMLA hill of the same state in 1917. The Apple cultivar “Ambri” is considered to be indigenous to Kashmir and had been grown long before western introduction in the country. Nearly all of the Indian apples are grown in the three mountainous states of north.

- Jammu and Kashmir
- Himachal Pradesh
- Uttaranchal Pradesh

J&K & Himachal Pradesh have roughly equal areas planted to apple even Himachal Pradesh have more land under apple cultivation but J&K has the high average yield & accounts for over 70% of total apple production of the country. Apple is a major fruit grown in Kashmir. Jammu And Kashmir State controls 49% of the land dedicated to apple cultivation in India, contributing more than 70% of the total apple production of the country. As per the survey carried out by the Global Consulting agency horticulture production of the state contributes about 45% of total agricultural production of the state, of which 80% is controlled by the production of apple fruit. Apple business in Jammu and Kashmir engages nearly 30 lakh people either directly or indirectly. From past few years the trend of converting the land into apple orchards has been rapidly increased. It has been increased from

47342 hectares in 1975-76 to 78007 hectares in 1995-96, which further increased to 143501 hectares in 2016-17. The cultivation of apple is done in all districts of Kashmir valley. Major contributors to apple production are Baramulla, Shopian, Pulwama, Kupwada, Anantnag, Kulgam etc.

Review of literature

Apple (*Malus pumila* L.) is undoubtedly the most important temperate fruits of Kashmir with an excellent keeping quality & wide variety of tastes & flavors. It is through the efforts of consciousness of beauty, taste & agro climatic conditions of valley which has made it ideally suited state for apples. Apple industry is a major sector of the economy of Kashmir valley & the fruit industry in the state indeed become the bull work of rural economy (*wani et al _1993*)

Rauf et al(2010) studied on “Economics of production and marketing of apples in Himachal Pradesh and Jammu and Kashmir.” Marketing aspect of the study indicated that channel (Producer-----pre harvest contractor----commission agent----retailer----consumer) was patronized by about 11% of the sample orchardists in Himachal Pradesh and more than 17% in Jammu and Kashmir. Channel (Producer---- commission agent---- Whole saler---- Retailer---- Consumer) is largest channel through which 56% of produce in Himachal Pradesh and 64% in Jammu and Kashmir are routed .

Malik (2013)” Apple production is the main occupation of the Kashmir valley, as it constitutes 90% of total fruit crop in the valley. But this sector faces lot of problems like improper marketing facilities, ignorance from government side, and lack of infrastructure”

“Jammu and Kashmir is the largest apple producing

state of India, but the state doesn't earn that from apple industry what it should have. The main problem of apple industry in Kashmir is the lack of marketing information and technique” Dr Musadiq Amen Shah.

“Horticulture is the most important income generating industry of Jammu and Kashmir, and Kashmir is an ideal region in the world for growing fresh and dry fruits. The demand for Kashmiri fruit within the country is huge and export potential is also very high. The fruit industry in Kashmir is generating Rs 600 crore revenue and providing employment to more than 33 lakh people directly or indirectly in the state” Ghulam Malik , General secretary Jammu and Kashmir K.T

Objectives of the present study

- 1: To study the district wise area and production of apples in Kashmir.
- 2: To study the dispatch of apple fruit to different national and international markets from fruit mandi Sopore.

Research Methodology

Keeping in view the objective of the study, the data collection was carried out both at primary & secondary level.

At primary level, data was collected by face to face unstructured interview. District Baramulla as being the highest apple producing district in the valley was given the special preference in data collection.

For the collection of secondary data various websites were consulted like SKUAST, J&K horticultural board, American horticultural board etc. Relevant material in the form of books & journals were also consulted for study. Data was also collected from the department of horticulture and other allied departments

Table: 1 Following data shows the area under apple cultivation in all the ten districts of Kashmir from 2012-2017
(Area in Hectares)

S.No	District	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17
1	Baramulla	24601	24675	24952	25203	25203
2	Kupwada	18942	18981	19012	19015	19107
3	Srinagar	3089	3114	3114	1410	1470
4	Bandipora	5605	5840	5994	6160	6174
5	Ganderbal	5716	6382	6725	6965	7310
6	Budgam	14649	14758	14912	12835	13015
7	Pulwama	11425	12389	12798	14143	14290
8	Shopian	20625	20685	21595	21607	21663
9	Kulgam	16766	17442	17153	18192	18207
10	Anantnag	16539	17119	17217	16971	17062
	Total	137957	141385	143472	142501	143501

Source (Horticulture Board Kashmir).

Table 2: District wise estimate of apple production of Kashmir from 2012-2017(Production in Mts)

S.No	District	2012-13	2013-14	2014-15	2015-16	2016-17
1	Baramulla	328035	510766	423637	529265	380005
2	Kupwada	203743	283444	105369	278657	257072
3	Srinagar	39281	39481	14490	18079	17064
4	Bandipora	65102	69147	30584	56143	64834
5	Ganderbal	51844	57146	48528	59768	59768
6	Budgam	85092	86047	31526	156081	132329
7	Pulwama	85095	110192	90182	145800	139288
8	Shopian	191506	204185	183412	248044	237001
9	Kulgam	120734	131749	57518	209205	207259
10	Anantnag	150285	136702	149391	214406	188148
	Total	1320717	1628859	1134637	1915448	1682768

Source (Horticulture Board Kashmir)

Data Analysis

Table 1 and table 2 shows the statistics regarding area and production of apples from the year 2012-13 to the year 2016-17. In the year 2012-13 the total area under apple cultivation was 137957 hectares while as the production in the same year was 1320717 metric tons. In the year 2013-14 the area under apple cultivation was 141385 hectares and the production in the same year was 1628859 metric tons. In the year 2014 -15 the total area was 143472 hectares and the production was

only 1134637 metric tons. The main cause of this low production was the sep.2014 floods. But after 2014-15 there was again the increasing trend in area and also in production. In 2015-16 the apple production in Kashmir was recorded as 1915448 metric tons, highest in previous 5 years and the area was also recorded as 142501 hectares. In 2016-17 a little decline trend was recorded in the production as compared to its previous year, it was because of the bad weather conditions. In this year the production was recorded as 1682768 metric tons and the area was 143501 hectares.

From the above statistics it was also found that the district Baramulla is a largest apple producing district in Kashmir. In 2012-13 it contributed 24.837% to the total apple production of Kashmir region and 31.357%, 37.34%, 27.631%, 22.582% respectively in 2013-14, 2014-15, 2015-16 and 2016-17.

Marketing Management

Marketing is a comprehensive function; it is concerned with every aspect of produce from its inception, design, pricing, distribution, setting & promotion until it finally reaches the hands of the consumers. The apple industry in India is concentrated in the western Himalayas, but the entire country is consumer of apples. It, therefore gives a virtual monopoly to these areas to supply apples to a very vast market. The producers position is more strengthened because when fruit matures in August & Sept, there is practically no other fresh fruit available in the Indian market. Kashmiri apples are dispatched almost to all national markets including Azad Pur fruit and vegetable mandi Delhi, Kolkata, Chennai, Hyderabad, Chandigarh, Bangalore, Jaipur and other markets. Kashmiri apples are also dispatched to other countries like Nepal, Pakistan and Bangladesh. Delhi is considered as the biggest and most suitable market for Kashmiri apples where loaded trucks remain unattended for several days due to very heavy arrivals

during the peak marketing months. Delhi is also the biggest wholesale supplying market dispatching stocks to different markets throughout the year.

Statement showing diversification of fruit dispatched from fruit mandi sopore to various terminal markets of the country as well as abroad for the marketing year 2014-15. Data shows the dispatch in boxes.

Table 3

Station	State	Total No. of Boxes
Srinagar	J&K	24400
Jammu	J&K	379200
Amritsar	Punjab	420400
Ludiahana	Do	35800
Jalandhar	Do	305600
Patiala	Do	33000
Rajpur	Do	2400
Ganganagar	Rajasthan	126400
Jodhpur	Do	43200
Jaipur	Do	158400
Chandigarh	Haryana	187600
Mansa	Do	141400
Ahmadabad	Gujarat	515200
Surratt	Do	21600
Kanpur	U.P	293400
Luknow	Do	444200
Mumbai	Maharashtra	548200
Hyderabad	A.P	90200
Delhi	U.T Capital	1445400
Dhaka	Bangladesh	394800
Total(boxes)		5610800

(Source: Marketing wing of Horticulture Department Sopore, District Baramulla)

Data Analysis

The above statistics shows that in the year 2014-15 the 25.761% of the total fruit was dispatched to Delhi, followed by Mumbai with 9.77%. and Mumbai was followed by Ahmadabad with 9.18% of the total fruit dispatched from fruit mandi sopore. The above statistics also shows that the apple fruit was also dispatched to Bangladesh which constitutes 7.036% of the total dispatch from the said mandi.

CONCLUSIONS:

Apple fruit is the 2nd among the most widely produced fruits in the world after banana. China is the largest apple producing country in the world, contributes over 50% of worlds total apple production. India is ranked as the 6th largest apple producing country in the world and 2nd in Asia after china. There is a scope for further production in India, it is because the agro climatic conditions of major apple producing states (J&K, Himachal Pradesh, Uttaranchal) are very favorable for apple production. Apple production plays a key role in the country's agricultural economy, so it needs an intensive attention of the Government. The economy of the Jammu and Kashmir state is largely depend upon its apple industry, as it plays important role in improving the standard of living of the state as whole and Kashmir in particular. From the above study it has been found that there is a rising trend in the area under apple cultivation in the Jammu and Kashmir. similar rising trend has been also witnessed in the overall apple production in the state. The apple fruits of the Kashmir valley are almost dispatched to all national fruit markets and also to some international markets like Pakistan, Bangladesh and Nepal.

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